

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Selenium(IV) by Manganese(III)

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The title reaction is first order each in oxidant and catalyst and retarded by Mn^{II} . The order in Se^{IV} is unity at lower concentrations and fractional at higher concentrations. Increase in $[H^+]$ retards the rate of the reaction but variation in ionic strength has negligible effect. A suitable mechanism involving Ru^{VIII} as active oxidising species is proposed.

Dikshitulu and coworkers¹ studied the Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidation of Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} by Ce^{IV} . They also observed that the kinetics and mechanism of Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidation of Te^{IV} by Ce^{IV} are considerably different from that by Tl^{III} . While Ru^{VIII} is considered to be the reactive species in the former reaction, Ru^V is regarded as the active oxidising species in the latter. Presuming that there may be a similar change in the mechanism of Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidation of Se^{IV} with change in oxidant, the authors have taken up a detailed kinetic and mechanistic study of Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidation of Se^{IV} by Mn^{III} in sulphuric acid medium.

Results and Discussion

The plots of log (absorbance) versus time were found to be linear well beyond two half-lives when $[Se^{IV}] \gg [Mn^{III}]$, indicating the order with respect to Mn^{III} to be unity. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants (k') obtained from the slopes of these plots at different initial concentrations of Mn^{III} were found to be fairly constant confirming unit order dependence of rate on $[Mn^{III}]$. The values of k' were however found to increase with increase in $[Se^{IV}]$ (Table 1), the plot of k' versus $[Se^{IV}]$ being a straight-line passing through origin upto a concentration of $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, indicating the order in $[Se^{IV}]$ to be unity. Beyond this concentration the order with respect to Se^{IV} is fractional. At constant concentrations of Mn^{III} , Se^{IV} and H^+ , the reaction was found to exhibit first order dependence on $[Ru^{III}]$ (Table 1). The product Se^{VI} did not show any effect on rate, but the other product Mn^{II} was found to retard the reaction at higher concentrations. Increase in ionic strength (maintained with $NaClO_4$) did not show any significant effect on k' (the small decrease in k' with increase in ionic strength may be merely a medium effect), indicating that at least one of the species participating in the transition state is neutral. Increase in $[H^+]$ as well as $[HSO_4^-]$ was found to cause a decrease in rate. The reaction was found to obey Arrhenius temperature dependence, k' values at 30, 35, 40 and 45° being 13.8×10^{-4} , 20.2×10^{-4} , $29.2 \times$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[Se^{IV}]$, $[Ru^{III}]$, $[Mn^{II}]$, $[H^+]$ AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) ON FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT (k')

Temp = 30 ± 0.1°						
$[Mn^{III}]$	$[Se^{IV}]$	$[Ru^{III}]$	$[Mn^{II}]$	$[H^+]$	μ	k'
10^4	10^3	10^6	10^3			
mol	mol	mol	mol	mol	mol	10^4
dm^{-3}	dm^{-3}	dm^{-3}	dm^{-3}	dm^{-3}	dm^{-3}	s^{-1}
5.0	10.0	5.0	100.0	2.0	2.0	1.9
10.0	10.0	5.0	100.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
15.0	10.0	5.0	100.0	2.0	2.0	2.1
20.0	10.0	5.0	100.0	2.0	2.0	2.1
25.0	10.0	5.0	100.0	2.0	2.0	2.2
5.0	2.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	2.9
5.0	4.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	5.6
5.0	6.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	8.5
5.0	8.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	11.2
5.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	14.0
5.0	20.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	18.2
5.0	40.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	24.5
5.0	60.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	39.8
5.0	80.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	44.5
5.0	100.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	50.0
10.0	10.0	1.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	3.0
10.0	10.0	2.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	5.2
10.0	10.0	4.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	10.5
10.0	10.0	6.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	15.7
10.0	10.0	8.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	20.7
10.0	10.0	10.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	25.7
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	13.8
10.0	10.0	5.0	10.0	2.0	2.0	7.8
10.0	10.0	5.0	20.0	2.0	2.0	4.7
10.0	10.0	5.0	40.0	2.0	2.0	2.5
10.0	10.0	5.0	60.0	2.0	2.0	1.6
10.0	10.0	5.0	80.0	2.0	2.0	1.2
10.0	10.0	5.0	100.0	2.0	2.0	1.0
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	5.0	10.7
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.5	5.0	9.0
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	3.0	5.0	8.3

Table-1(Contd.)

10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	3.5	5.0	8.0
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	4.0	5.0	7.2
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.0	13.7
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	2.5	13.3
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	3.0	12.8
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	3.5	12.3
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	4.0	11.9
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	4.5	11.4
10.0	10.0	5.0	5.8	2.0	5.0	11.0

10^{-4} , $43.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The activation parameters E_a and ΔS^\ddagger at 30° computed by linear least-squares method were found to be $60.8 \pm 1.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-69.0 \pm 4.2 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

In 2.0 to 4.0 mol dm^{-3} aqueous sulphuric acid medium employed in the present investigation, Mn^{III} exists in the form of Mn^{3+} , MnOH^{2+} and MnSO_4^+ . In acid solutions, Se^{IV} exists both in monomeric and dimeric forms depending on the concentration of Se^{IV} . Upto a $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ of 1.0×10^{-2} employed in this investigation (other than $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ variation studies), the percentage of monomer is $>92\%$. Further, since the dissociation constant of selenous acid is 3.0×10^{-3} at 25°C , it may be inferred that under the experimental conditions almost all the Se^{IV} exists in the form of H_2SeO_3 only.

The previous workers^{4,5} while studying the kinetics of Ru-catalysed oxidation of As^{III} by Ce^{IV} sulphate, pointed out that Ru present in lower oxidation states will be converted into Ru^{VIII} form within 10 s. Also, Ru^{III} shows the same catalytic activity as RuO_4 of the same concentration and that the latter is the actual oxidising species. Dikshitulu *et al.*¹ made a similar observation in the Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidation of Se^{IV} and Te^{IV} by Ce^{IV} sulphate. In the present investigation also it has been observed that when aqueous solutions of Ru^{III} are mixed with excess of Mn^{III} , Ru^{III} is readily and quantitatively oxidised to RuO_4 . Hence the actual oxidising species involved in the present investigation also may be regarded as RuO_4 . When golden yellow coloured RuO_4 solutions are mixed with excess of Se^{IV} the resultant solution is invariably found to have a light green colour which is characteristic of Ru^{VI} (had reduction occurred to still lower oxidation states, the colour of the resultant solution would have been reddish brown). On the basis of these observations, the following mechanism is proposed :

This mechanism leads to the rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = k_4[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_e [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (9)$$

Assuming stationary-state kinetics for Ru^{VIII} ,

$$[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_e = \frac{[\text{Ru}^{\text{VII}}]_e \{k_1[\text{Mn}^{3+}]_e + k_2[\text{MnOH}^{2+}]_e + k_3[\text{MnSO}_4^+]_e\}}{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3}[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]) + k_4[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]} \quad (10)$$

Substituting for $[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_e$ from equation (10) in equation (9),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_4[\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_e [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] \\ &= \frac{k_4[\text{Ru}^{\text{VII}}]_e \{k_1[\text{Mn}^{3+}]_e + k_2[\text{MnOH}^{2+}]_e + k_3[\text{MnSO}_4^+]_e\} [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]}{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3}[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]) + (k_4[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}])} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t = [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_e + [\text{MnOH}^{2+}]_e + [\text{MnSO}_4^+]_e \quad (12)$$

Substituting for $[\text{Mn}^{3+}]_e$, $[\text{MnOH}^{2+}]_e$ and $[\text{MnSO}_4^+]_e$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{k_4[\text{Ru}^{\text{VII}}]_e [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] \left\{ \frac{k_1[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + k_h + K[\text{HSO}_4^-]} + \frac{k_2 k_n [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t}{[\text{H}^+] + k_h + k[\text{HSO}_4^-]} + \frac{k_3 k [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{HSO}_4^-]}{[\text{H}^+] + k_h + k[\text{HSO}_4^-]} \right\}}{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3}[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]) + k_4[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]} \\ &= \frac{k_4[\text{Ru}^{\text{VII}}]_e [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] (k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2 k_h + k_3 k [\text{HSO}_4^-])}{([\text{H}^+] + k_h + k[\text{HSO}_4^-]) \{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3}[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]) + k_4[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]\}} \end{aligned}$$

Further, in view of the rapid oxidation of Ru^{III} to Ru^{VII} and in view of large excess of Mn^{III} compared to Ru^{III} , $[\text{Ru}^{\text{VII}}]_e$ may be replaced by $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t$ and hence

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_4 [\text{Ru}^{\text{VII}}]_e [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] (k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 k_h + k_3 k [\text{HSO}_4^-])}{([\text{H}^+] + k_h + k [\text{HSO}_4^-]) ([\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3} [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + k_4 [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}])} \quad (13)$$

The rate equation (13) explains the first order dependence of rate on $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$ and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$. It also explains first order dependence on Se^{IV} at lower concentrations where the term $k_4 [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ in the denominator is small, as well as fractional order dependence on Se^{IV} at higher concentrations, where the term $k_4 [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ becomes comparable to the other terms.

The pseudo-first order rate constant k' ($\text{Rate}/\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}$) may be written as

$$k' = \frac{k_4 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]_t (k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 k_h + k_3 k [\text{HSO}_4^-])}{([\text{H}^+] + k_h + k [\text{HSO}_4^-]) ([\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3} [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + k_4 [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}])} \quad (14)$$

Transposing the above equation,

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]_t (k_{-1} + k_{-2} + k_{-3} [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]) ([\text{H}^+] + k_h + k [\text{HSO}_4^-])}{k_4 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]_t (k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 k_h + k_3 k [\text{HSO}_4^-])} + \frac{([\text{H}^+] + k_h + k [\text{HSO}_4^-])}{[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_t (k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 k_h + k_3 k [\text{HSO}_4^-])} \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) predicts that the plot of $1/k'$ versus $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ should be a straight-line with an intercept on rate axis. The experimental curve is similar to the one expected, thus substantiating the proposed mechanism.

The kinetic pattern in the Ru^{III} -catalysed oxidation of Se^{IV} by Mn^{III} is considerably different from that involving Ce^{IV} as oxidant. Although the order with respect to $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ is unity in both the reactions, the order with respect to $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$ is unity in the former reaction while that with respect to Ce^{IV} is zero in the latter. Similarly, the order with respect to Se^{IV} is also different in the two reactions; at low $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ while it is unity in Mn^{III} oxidation, it is fractional in Ce^{IV} oxidation. Complexation between Ru^{VIII} and Se^{IV} which was assumed in Ce^{IV} oxidation in perchloric acid medium is insignificant in sulphuric acid medium (probably because of competition from sulphate ion for complexation) which explains the observed unit order with respect to Se^{IV} in Mn^{III} oxidation. Incidentally, this also explains the decrease in rate with increase in $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ observed in the present reaction. The existence of reverse reaction between Ru^{VIII} and Mn^{II} and the absence of such a reaction between Ru^{VIII} and Ce^{III} also seem to be responsible for the difference in kinetic pattern between Mn^{III} and Ce^{IV} oxidations.

It is interesting to note that although the kinetic pattern is considerably different with the two oxidants, Ru^{VIII} (probably in the form of RuO_4) is the active oxidising species in both the reactions. Further, the mechanism of oxidation of Se^{IV} by Mn^{III} seems to involve a two-electron transfer, since vinyl polymerization has not been observed during the course of the reaction.

Experimental

An aqueous solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) of Se^{IV} was prepared from sodium selenite (E. Merck, Pro Analyti) and its strength verified⁶. An aqueous solution of Se^{VI} was prepared from sodium selenate (AnalaR). A solution (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) of Mn^{II} in $2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was prepared from manganese(II) sulphate (Sarabhai Merck, Pro Analyti). A solution (0.02 mol dm^{-3}) of Mn^{III} in H_2SO_4 (4.0 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared afresh by slowly adding potassium permanganate (AnalaR; 0.01 mol dm^{-3}) to an ice-cold solution (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) of Mn^{II} ⁷ and standardised by titration against standard Fe^{II} solution using ferroin as indicator. The absorbance of the standardised Mn^{III} solution was measured at 350 nm and a relationship was thus established between absorbance and $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$. Thereafter, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$ was determined by measuring its absorbance. A solution ($0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of ruthenium(III) sulphate in H_2SO_4 (2.0 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared from ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Mathey) after expelling chloride by fuming with concentrated H_2SO_4 and the solution standardised⁴. An aqueous solution of Ru^{VIII} was prepared⁸ from Ru^{III} solution. Sodium perchlorate solution (8.0 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared by neutralising anhydrous Na_2CO_3 (AnalaR) with 70% HClO_4 (Merck, Pro Analyti). All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

The kinetics of the reaction were studied in $2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless mentioned. The reaction was monitored using a Shimadzu UV-140.02 spectrophotometer following the absorbance of Mn^{III} at 350 nm ($\epsilon = 2.0 \times 10^2$), where all other ions involved had negligible absorption. All kinetic runs were carried out under the conditions $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] \gg [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$. The rate constants are reproducible within an error of $\pm 2\%$. The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing known amounts of Se^{IV} to react completely with two- to four-fold excess of Mn^{III} in $2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in presence of $10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Ru}^{\text{III}}$. After about 1 h, the unreacted $[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$ was determined spectro-photometrically. After applying a suitable blank correction for the decomposition of Mn^{III} , one mol of Se^{IV} was found to correspond to 2 mol of Mn^{III} .

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